

Madness and Reason in Stephen King's Gothic Heroines

Maria Iustinica Roată

University of Craiova

Received: 16.01.2025 | Accepted: 18.01.2025 | Published: 21.01.2025

*Corresponding Author: Maria Iustinica Roată

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14713068](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14713068)

Abstract

Original Research Article

The woman as a character has always been the muse of Gothic writers. Her intelligence and adapting ability to hostile challenging situations ensured her final triumph over evil. Madness and reason are constant coordinates of Stephen King's Gothic heroine, accentuating her drama or accelerating her fateful denouement.

This article aims to offer an unedited approach to some existential dilemmas about human consciousness versatility that Stephen King has intensely exploited in his novels over the years. Carrie White is the bullied, ostracized teenager, Wendy Torrance confronts her husband's growing madness in the phantasmagorical *Overlook*, and Annie Wilkes doses her madness according to the degree of satisfaction provided by her favourite novel.

The majority of Gothic novels expose women to inequities and dangerous situations. Unlike the English Gothic, where the heroines faced bizarre situations, in America, the female characters are prisoners of their own minds. The psyche is tormented by an evil spirit, symbolising irreversible human degradation. The challenges are unequal battles in which the protagonists must exceed their limits. Their victory is the triumph of good over evil and life over death.

Keywords: Woman, Gothic Heroine, Madness, Psychic

INTRODUCTION

Stephen King has revived the traditional Gothic heroine, took her out of the domestic sphere, and transposed her into the Gothic world of crime and mystery. The study of the Gothic heroine presents the multivalent character, fragile and strong in equal measure, able to face destiny with dignity and get out of the prison of her own mind to enjoy the freedom of the spirit, the joy of victory, and the reconciliation with the self.

Like the traditional Gothic hero, the Gothic heroine has a rich history in secular Gothic literature. Ellen Moers argues that the *Gothic Female*¹ is 'a coded expression of women's fears of entrapment within the domestic and within the female body'

(Smith & Wallace 2004: 1). Thus, the women's entrapment was within the absolute patriarchy, submissive and resignedly accepting their condition of 'domestic objects' used for household cleaning, to give birth, and to take care of their children. The traditional Gothic conventions (the haunted castle, the ghost, and the supernatural- either explained or not-) were replaced with the savage interest in the human mind and family histories.

Then, would the woman have deserved to rise above her condition?

Some critics have pointed out that the use of terms like *women's Gothic*, *feminine Gothic*, and *Gothic feminism* is

¹ In *Literary Women*, Ellen Moers coined the term *Gothic Female* when speaking about the female Gothic writers. Although the *American Gothic* traces its roots to the British, this material has mentioned that America's writers much closer to the contemporaneous society, to offer a better image for

our topic. But it is imperative to remember women writers like Ann Radcliffe, Mary Shelley, and the Brontes who were exponential for the Gothic tradition and transfigured their realities into Gothic fantasies.

exactly what Moers is referring to. The Gothic woman is a heroine and a victim at the same time. Gothicism depicts the psychological and physical violence against women who are often seen as the natural victims of society. Their abuse can take many forms, including rape (Margaret White, from *Carrie*; Beverly Marsh, from *It*), brutal beating (Rosie, from *Rose Madder*), humiliation (Carrie White, from the eponymous novel), psychological and physical abuse (Wendy Torrance, from *The Shining*).

Gothic fiction represents the metaphor of osmosis between past and future times, connecting and disconnecting the old genetic family code to the need to continue the cultural, social, or family tradition. As Diana Wallace argues:

‘The conflict between societal repression and women’s inner impulses surfaced in the Gothic text and culminated in the horrid actions of the Gothic hero/villain’; furthermore, ‘the Female Gothic...is shaped by many issues, including national identity, sexuality, language, race and history. It is also the case that the form challenges and complicates such issues and this is why it is of such major literary and cultural importance.’ (Wallace 10)

LITERATURE REVIEW

In England, the Gothic heroine is overwhelmed with fears and anxieties because of their persistent persecution by older men or ‘men in the rampage’ (Ellis 2000: 264). The women from Anne Radcliffe’s novels depend on a brave man, usually a nobleman, to save them and offer the much-desired place in the society married women, reduced to ‘ghosts’ or the ‘living dead’ by law, exist as supposed ghosts... The law itself engenders the supernatural; women are the ghosts in its machine (Clery 126). Marriage was a whole life imprisonment in the Bastille.

Charlotte Bronte’s *Jane Eyre* (1847) was an example of the feminine ideal that the Victorians wanted to construct; Emily Bronte’s *Wuthering Heights* demonstrated that women’s rights were respected in the Gothic conventions as Mary Wollstonecraft had stated years before. Bertha Mason, the epitome of madness, represents the societal crushing of women and their manipulation through the machinery of conventional marriage and the theft of personal independence. The opposite of Bertha’s madness is the brilliance of Jane Eyre’s balanced reason that refuses the enclosure or amputation of her principles by the totalitarian patriarchal society.

Trying to adapt feminist desires to the framework of male society defeats the rational behaviour of Emily Bronte’s heroes. Heathcliff and Catherine Earnshaw experience the madness born of their passion for each other, which sickens reason and shares revenge.

In America, the author focuses primarily on women’s psyche, alternating past, present, and future periods. The

settings go from the rural landscapes to the immensely architectural buildings. In American literature, there is always a reminiscence of the evil, as the book reader or the film viewer does not have the certainty of its complete annihilation. On the contrary, there is always the threat of its return.

In 1976, Ellen Moers defined the ‘female Gothic’ as the ‘paraphernalia of claustrophobic castles, villainous dominating men, and beleaguered heroines to thematise women’s sense of isolation and imprisonment within a domestic ideology fast becoming hegemonic by the end of the eighteenth century.’ (Moers 1976: 122-140)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND FINDINGS

Stephen King’s gothic heroines present the themes of madness and sick jealousy that darken reason and pollute feelings. This article combines interdisciplinary qualitative rather than quantitative methods from the literary, philosophical, and metaphysical domains. Its purpose is to bring forth dominant issues of the corroded society, like mental sanity, domestic abuse, and bullying. Rigorous investigation and scrupulous analysis are the tools the author uses to achieve her goals.

This material aims to make readers aware of the Gothic heroine’s abilities and importance in literature, sparking interest in an effective comparison between the traditional and modern Gothic woman in contemporary society.

A responsible woman maintains family unity, shapes the behaviours of its members, and promotes social balance. She fulfils a catalyst function, campaigning for peace, understanding, and moderation in the consumerist society.

The article aims to delineate the concept of the Gothic heroine as a unique cultural construct, capable of restoring things to their original state. The Gothic heroine faces mundane or extramundane challenges and protects the family from evil external forces, possessing a natural ability to restore social order through perseverance and fighting spirit.

The selection of some works from Stephen King’s gallery, such as *Carrie* or *The Shining*, aims to arouse the reader’s curiosity about the psychology of the Gothic heroine. Also, the close reading of the texts has as main objective to stimulate the critical thinking of readers who want to deepen their knowledge about the personality of the Gothic heroine.

Isolation and bullying are predominant in *Carrie* (1974), the high school teenager, long abused by her peers and vehemently rejected by an implacable, domineering religious mother.

Carrie plays two major parts in the novel. First, she is the unhappy outcast and her school colleagues’ bullying target; she is described as ‘a frog among the swans’, chubby, freckled and with unkempt blond hair, totally unsuited to the world of

Chamberlain, Maine. Her tyrannical religious mother, Margaret White, has never loved Carrie and has always submitted the girl to psychological abuse.

The second part presents Carrie as an interesting object of study; she is more of a symbol than a character struggling to survive in a cruel and incomprehensible world. Carrie leads an austere life, where there is no room for love; she is ostracized and deprived of her childhood; as a teenager, Margaret denied her elementary knowledge about physical development; in the sequence developed in the shower room, Carrie considers menstruation a sign of imminent death that God has sent to punish the girl for her sins.

Two things are consequent to this episode: the first, Sue Snell feels guilty about Carrie's humiliation and wants to make up things, asking Tommy Ross, her boyfriend to be Carrie's partner at the prom; the second is the irreversible trigger of her emotional crisis that leads to an inevitable cruel fate. More than a gothic heroine, Carrie is the tragic heroine of her own prejudices. She is like a modern Cinderella but with a different end. In her madness, triggered on the night of the prom when buckets of pig's blood are thrown over her and Tommy Ross, Carrie uses her telekinetic powers and punishes the whole town for her misfortune. Only Sue is spared by this tragic end.

Carrie has become an iconic character in contemporary cinema. The first version, aired two years after the publication of the book (November, 3rd 1976), had the actress Sissy Spacek as protagonist and Brian de Palma as director. Despite the differences from the book, the film was a resounding success. Sissy Spacek gave a masterful performance that earned her a nomination for best actress. Piper Laurie who played the diabolical Margaret White, was also nominated for Best Supporting Actress.

The most accurate adaptation and the closest to the novel was written by Bryan Fuller and directed by David Carson, in 2002. In the 2013 version of *Carrie*, the protagonist was Chloe Grace Moretz, the production was signed by Kevin Misher and the screenplay was written by Leonard Cohen. It was directed by Kimberley Peirce. Although the films differ from the book, the main idea is the same: Carrie's struggle to be accepted in society, her revenge and, finally, her tragic death. For instance, in the scene when Carrie comes back from the prom and prepares to kill her mother: the book says that with her supernatural powers, Carrie stops her mother's heart... without having previously taken a shower; then, at the prom scene Chris is filmed to upload the video with the pig blood on the social reds, but in the book, there is no smartphone or other device to record the scene.

Like Carrie, Wendy Torrance from *The Shining* (1977) had to endure an authoritarian mother, always nervous and unhappy. Insults and emotional attacks led to a kind of mental imbalance, which manifests itself through long and uncontrollable bouts of crying. Wendy is delicate but depressed. She is a stay-at-home wife and her marriage is tense. In the Overlook, until Jack's madness, she supports her husband and her son. She understands and trusts little Danny's visions and constantly asks for his advice.

Both Wendy and her husband, Jack Torrance, come from families with abusive parents. She is Danny's partner in finding the escape route and his main ally in the fight against the demons in the Overlook. Wendy is the deuteragonist² of *The Shining*. Her role is carefully analysed, being respected for her place in society and her strength to save her child. Her gradual evolutions 'from an independent girl to a mature woman, as well as motherhood, makes this character a new model of interpretation of the Gothic genre, in the style of Stephen King.' (Frank 1990:47)

The complexity of love and the imminence of death are fundamental themes of the novel *Pet Sematary* (1983). Rachel Creed feels terrible anguish when thinking about her sister, Zelda's disease, back in childhood. The idea of death haunts Rachel's past and present which aligns with the tradition of the Gothic character, which cannot live peacefully because of unhealed wounds. Her inability to free herself from the mortifications of the past unleashes her exacerbated fear of death, and the tensions she lives in betray the limits of this Gothic heroine. The supernatural and isolation have sealed her tragedy.

In the twentieth century the concept of the gothic female no longer referred to the gender of the writer or the dominance of men over women but also included different styles and plots. In *Dr Sleep* (2013), the novel sequel, Wendy Torrance who had already been seriously injured in the explosion at the Overlook, lived with her son in Florida. She passed away because of lung cancer, in 1999.

Wendy Torrance's traumatic past matches her husband's violent temper. The desolation and sterility of the Overlook Hotel deepen the tragedy of this Gothic heroine. The power of endurance, specific to the Gothic genre, transforms Wendy Torrance, from the victim of her husband, Jack into the saviour of their son, Danny. The woman's emotional turmoil exceeds the limits of a character who is, in principle, an unfortunate victim of circumstances.

Wendy's fight with her husband and the darkness of the Overlook Hotel is the parable of the eternal fight between good and evil, a pillar of the classic Gothic narrative. Stephen King

² The deuteragonist is the equivalent of the secondary main character who supports or opposes the protagonist (wiki sources).

brings realistic and postmodernist elements to the image of his gothic heroine, placing the supernatural and the grotesque on the versatility of the human mind.

Beyond the status of the postmodern Gothic heroine is the personality of the devoted mother, who fights hard to save her son from the clutches of darkness. The maternal instinct defines the Gothic character, giving it distinction and suppleness. Her protective side brings out both the vulnerability and strength of the Gothic heroine.

Wendy's transformation from a loving mother and devoted wife sparked the interest of filmmakers for a screenplay of the female character from *The Shining*. The director Stanley Kubrick tasked the actress Shelley Duvall with the transition from the passive figure to the hyperactive woman. The play of lights amplified the fragility of the heroine on screen. The wide-open eyes and uncontrolled tremors suggest her psychological state. The sequence in which Jack (Jack Nicholson) chases her with the axe denotes the activation of the woman's defensive instincts, in the face of domestic abuse and the husband's descent into the final abyss of betrayal of his family.

Anne Wilkes, from the novel *Misery* (1987), oscillates dramatically between reason and madness, when the novel of her adored writer, Paul Sheldon, does not meet her expectations. The sincere affection for the writer who becomes Anne's prisoner alternates with episodes of inexplicable violence, resulting in the physical and mental mutilation of the victim.

Isolation and total control rise above the gothic settings in Stephen King's novels. The Gothic heroine exceeds her limits and becomes a bastion of terror. Her tragedy is the consequence of past traumas and mental instability. Until the end of the ages, the delight of death is the delirious and enduring fate of Gothic heroines.

CONCLUSIONS

The multifaceted characters of Stephen King symbolize the understanding of his subjects' behaviours in the domestic, social, and moral-civic spheres. Stephen King's gothic heroine means mercy, sacrifice, and rising above troubles through courage, dignity, and ambition.

Carrie's criminal behaviour is not the product of a morbid pleasure, but an automatic self-defence mechanism triggered from her sufferance. Wendy Torrance finds the strength within herself to protect her son from the evil forces of the Overlook Hotel. She fights with determination to keep her sanity in the madness created by her husband's gradual fall into sin.

Stephen King has created the complete Gothic heroine, capable of resilience, rebellion, and change. Her fight is the fight of all abused, marginalized, and discriminated women in contemporary society. Her motivation is equality and justice in the world and her desire will continue to inspire generations.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Clery, E.J., *The Rise of Supernatural Fiction 1762-1800*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995.
- Frederick S. Frank, *Through the Pale Door: A Guide to and through the American Gothic*, New York: Greenwood, 1990.
- Gilbert, Sandra M., and Susan Gubar. *The Madwoman in the Attic: the Women Writer and the Nineteenth-Century Literary Imagination*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 1984. Print.
- King, Stephen: *Carrie*, Hodder & Stoughton , London, 2011
- King, Stephen: *The Shining*, Anchor Books, New York, 2012.
- Magistrale, Anthony: *Stephen King: The Second Decade, 'Danse Macabre' to 'The Dark Half'*, Twayne Publishers, New York, 1992;
- Moers, Ellen: *Literary Women*, Doubleday & Co. , New York, 1976
- Reino, Joseph: *Stephen King, The First Decade, 'Carrie' to 'Pet Sematary'*, Twayne Publishing, Boston, 1988.
- Wallace, Diana. "The Haunting Idea": *Female Gothic Metaphors and Feminist Theory*." *The Female Gothic New Directions*, edited by Wallace and Smith, New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009.